

DIFFERENTIAL PRINCIPLES OF NEOLOGISMS AND REALIA

Daminov Navruz Kudratovich

(SamSIFL)

Yuldoshova Nargiza Yarashboyevna

(SamSIFL)

ANNOTATION

The article discusses the terms of realia and neologism, and the challenges which translator should render them into target language and culture; differential sides of two terms are explained in the article and the criteria affecting the choice of translator when applying them in real translation practice.

Key words: *culture, source language, realia, target culture, translation, equivalency, target language, neologism, standard language.*

Neologism and realia are two linguistic terms that refer to different sides of language use. Neologisms are newly introduced into the lexicon of a language,(1) while realia are words or phrases borrowed from another language to describe a specific culture or social practice. Both neologism and realia have differential sides that impact how they are used and understood in communication. Neologisms are often created to fill a gap in the language, to express a new concept, or to reflect new changes in society. For example, the word “selfie” was coined to describe the act of taking a picture of oneself using a smartphone. Neologisms can also be created through the blending of existing words, such as “brunch” (breakfast+lunch) or “smog” (smoke+fog). While neologisms are useful in expanding the vocabulary of a

language, they can also be challenging for non-native speakers who may not be familiar with the new terms.

Realia, on the other hand, are words or phrases that are borrowed from another language to describe a specific cultural or social practice. For instance, the word “sushi” is a realia borrowed from Japanese to describe a type of food. Realia can also include words borrowed from other languages to describe cultural practices, such as “fiesta” (Spanish for party) or “karma”(Sanskrit for action or deed). (4) While realia can add richness and diversity to a language, they can also be confusing for non-native speakers who may not be familiar with the cultural practices they describe.

The usage of neologism and realia in literature. In literature, neologisms and realia can be used to create a sense of authenticity and cultural specificity. For example, Gabriel Garcia Marquez’s “One hundred years of solitude” he uses realia such as “macondo” (a fictional town in Colombia) and “gypsies” (a group of travelling people with a specific cultural identity) to create a sense of futuristic technology or concepts, such as “teleportation” or “cyberspace”. The use of both terms in literature may lead the readers to misunderstandings who may not be familiar with the language or culture being described. In some cases, authors may provide explanations or context for these terms, while in others, readers may need to rely on their own knowledge or research to fully understand the text.(2)

Neologisms and realia in translation process. In translation, both of these terms pose a challenge as they may not have direct equivalents in the target language. Translators must carefully consider how to convey the intended meaning and cultural specificity of these terms while also ensuring that the translation is understandable and natural for readers in the target language. Translators may choose to use a variety of strategies to handle neologisms and realia, such as transliteration, borrowing or creating new words or phrases in the target language. They may also provide explanations or footnotes to help readers understand the cultural context and meaning of these terms. However, it is important for translators to be aware that their choices

may impact the overall tone and the style of translated text. They must balance the need for accuracy and cultural specificity with the desire to maintain the author's voice and style. Although neologisms and realia are important aspects of translation process, they require careful consideration and handling in translation to ensure that the intended meaning and cultural specificity are conveyed effectively in the target language.

While neologism introduce new ideas and concepts, realia reflect the unique characteristics of a particular culture or community. The differential sides of both terms impact how they are used and understood in communication and translation process.

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